

不存在奇完全数

黄山

(芜湖职业技术学院, 安徽, 芜湖, 241003)

摘要: 将多个素数的次幂和与完全数联系起来。

关键词: 完全数, 奇完全数, 素数的次幂和。

这个很简单, 类似于否定欧拉乘积公式那个过程。

$\forall m, n, k, d, n_k \in \mathbf{N}, \forall p, p_k, \in$ 素数。

$\forall p^n$ 的约数, 例如, $p^0, p^1, p^2, p^3, p^4, \dots, p^n$, $\forall p^n$ 的约数和, $S_p = \sum_{m=0}^n p^m = \frac{p^{n+1}-p^0}{p-1}$ 。

所以, $\forall \prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}$ 的约数和, $S_{\prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}} = \prod_{k=0}^m \frac{p_k^{n_k+1}-p_k^0}{p_k-1}$,

如果, $\frac{S_{\prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}}}{\prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}} = 2$, $\forall \prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}$ 就被称为完全数。

即, $\prod_{k=0}^m \frac{p_k^{n_k+1}-p_k^0}{(p_k-1)p_k^{n_k}} = 2$, $\prod_{k=0}^m \frac{p_k^{n_k+1}-p_k^0}{p_k-1} = 2 \prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}$,

解这个等式, 当且仅当 $2^{d+1} - 2^0 = p$, $\forall \prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k} = 2^d * p$ 有正整数解,

而 $2^d * p$ 为偶数, 所以, 不存在奇完全数。

参考文献: 无。

There is no odd perfect number

HuangShan

(Wuhu Institute of Technology, China, Wuhu, 241003)

Abstract: Associate the sum of the powers of multiple primes with complete numbers.

Key words: perfect numbers, Odd perfect numbers, the sum of the powers of primes.

This is very simple, similar to the process of negating the Euler product formula.

$\forall m, n, k, d, n_k \in \mathbb{N}, \forall p, p_k, \in \text{prime numbers}$.

Divisor of $\forall p^n$, Such as, $p^0, p^1, p^2, p^3, p^4, \dots, p^n$, Sum of divisors of $\forall p^n$, $S_n = \sum_{m=0}^n p^m = \frac{p^{n+1} - p^0}{p - 1}$.

So, Sum of divisors of $\forall \prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}$, $S_{\prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}} = \prod_{k=0}^m \frac{p_k^{n_k+1} - p_k^0}{p_k - 1}$,

If, $\frac{S_{\prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}}}{\prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}} = 2$, $\forall \prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}$ is called a perfect number.

That is, $\prod_{k=0}^m \frac{p_k^{n_k+1} - p_k^0}{(p_k - 1)p_k^{n_k}} = 2$, $\prod_{k=0}^m \frac{p_k^{n_k+1} - p_k^0}{p_k - 1} = 2 \prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k}$,

Solve this equation, If and only if $2^{d+1} - 2^0 = p$, $\forall \prod_{k=0}^m p_k^{n_k} = 2^d * p$ Have positive integer solution,

While $2^d * p$ is an even number, so there is no odd perfect number.

Reference: none.